

MECHANICAL AND MICROSTRUCTURE EVALUATION OF IN-SITU TITANIUM MATRIX COMPOSITE PROCESSED BY SEVERE PLASTIC DEFORMATION

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ABSTRACT

In situ synthesized TiB+TiC/Ti6Al4V titanium matrix composite with a strongly clustered TiB fibers and TiC particles distribution is successfully subjected to equal channel pressing (ECAP) at a temperature of 800 °C. The evolution of the microstructure and mechanical properties (yield strength, ultimate tensile strength and elongation) of TiB+TiC/Ti6Al4V during this thermo-mechanical processing is studied. The number of ECAP-Bc varies in the range of 1-4. The microstructure is more refined with the increasing number of ECAP passes. Formation of homogenous TiB short fibers and TiC particles with some ultrafine grains and sub-grains are observed after 4 ECAP passes. Strength increase with the increasing number of ECAP numbers and saturate after 4 ECAP passes to yield strength of 1180MPa, the ductility after ECAP 4 passes is much higher compare with the first ECAP pass, while maintain adequate levels of elongation to failure. The strengthening effect of small size reinforcements was also significant since its distribution was more homogeneous in the matrix.

1 INTRODUCTION

In the last decades, due to the remarkable physical and mechanical properties, ultrafine-grained (UFG) materials produced by severe plastic deformation (SPD) have been the subject of many study works [1~3]. Such ultrafine grained microstructures, usually in the range from 100nm to 1000 nm, provide a reasonable compromise between high strength and excellent ductility, which is especially attractive used in structural application [4]. This SPD processes can be defined as metal forming process in which a very high level of strain is applied to the materials during processing [5]. Among the known methods of severe plastic deformation, such as equal channel angular pressing, cyclic extrusion compression [6], torsion compression [7], multi-axis forging [8], and accumulated roll bonding [9]. Equal channel angular pressing is considered the most prospective candidate for practical applications [10]. The properties of materials processed by ECAP are strongly dependent on the plastic deformation behavior during pressing, which is governed mainly by die geometry and process variables. To obtain the excellent mechanical properties from ultrafine-grained microstructure, various materials like Al, Cu, Ti, Mg and their alloys have been applied to ECAP technology. For example, H. Paul et al [11] successfully deformed commercial purity AA3104 aluminum alloy via equal channel angular pressing to different strains to obtain a state of partial recrystallization. K. Bryla et al [12] investigated the grain refinement in AZ31 magnesium alloy processed by ECAP and studied the microstructure evolution and hardness response. For Ti and Ti alloys, most of the investigations related to ECAP on titanium and its alloys have been successfully confirmed to process samples especially CP-Ti, Ti6Al4V, metastable β titanium alloys and Ti-Ni alloys. Kang, et al [13] studied the mechanical behavior and microstructure evolution of CP-Ti in enhanced multi-pass ECAP and cold extrusion, the results showed that the ultimate tensile strength of CP-Ti increased remarkably from 295.5MPa to 791.9 MPa with significant refinement of the microstructure. Ko, et al [14] investigated the effect of initial microstructure on the formability of Ti6Al4V alloy, their work reported that most α and β grains were significantly refined to 0.2-0.3 μ m in diameter consisting of high angle grain

boundaries, the tensile strengths were extremely improved by the ECAP process. However, these previous works focused on the pure Ti and titanium alloys. There are few reports on ECAP of titanium matrix composite with higher strength. From above literature investigation, Most studies on ECAP have concentrated on pure metals and metallic alloys. Some limited studies are available on application of ECAP on metal matrix composites [15]. However, most of these limited reports are primary Al metal matrix composites. Much less reports are found on titanium matrix composite.

Titanium matrix composites (TMCs) with better properties can be prepared by in situ technique, which overcomes the shortcoming of traditional techniques, such as the problems of pollution of reinforcements and wettability between ceramic particles and matrix encountered in the casting technology. Therefore, in situ synthesized TMCs have been widely used in the literatures [16]. Generally, extensive studies have pointed out that TiB short fibers and TiC particles are the best reinforcements for titanium matrix composite. But the incorporation of high modulus and high strength reinforcements into titanium, it makes titanium matrix composite possessing high specific strength but low ductility at room and elevated temperature. Moreover, Lu, et al [17] investigated the reinforcements usually showed different shapes such as short-fiber shape, dendritic shape and equiaxed or near equiaxed shape by using common casting technology. Sun, et al [18] reported that these reinforcements were on a large range of 2~50 μm , which dispersed in a homogeneous manner in the composite. To solve this problem, it is useful to use a severe plastic deformation technology to homogenize the reinforcements in the composite. ECAP has a high hydrostatic pressure and shear strain, which can refine the grains and make the reinforcements distribute homogeneously [19]. Hence, it is of interest to apply ECAP process for fabricating the titanium matrix composite [20].

In this study, the Ti6Al4V alloy is used as matrix alloy of the composite for its good mechanical properties and wide applicability in the industries, the composite is manufactured from the in situ chemical reaction between Ti6Al4V and B₄C addition, and the microstructure and mechanical properties with increasing the number of ECAP passes were investigated for (TiB+TiC)/Ti6Al4V composite. Although a considerable amount of work had shown that Ti6Al4V alloy can achieve a better balance between high strength and good ductility utilizing the ECAP technique. Rare literatures have been focused on the titanium matrix composite processed by ECAP. Therefore, it is extremely useful to investigate the mechanical and microstructure evolution of ECAP processed (TiB+TiC)/Ti6Al4V composites.

2 EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

2.1 Sample preparation

The studied material TiB+TiC/Ti6Al4V composites are fabricated into the ingots with a diameter of Φ 120mm by a consumable vacuum arc-remelting furnace (Fig. 1). The raw materials are sponge Ti, B₄C powder (98%, average particles size 5-10 μm), and other alloying element is Al, Al-V. The stoichiometric amounts of the raw materials are blended together thoroughly and then compacted in to pellets. The pellets are melted in to the consumable vacuum arc-remelting furnace. The materials are melted at least twice to promote the microstructure homogeneity and fabricated into in ingots with a diameter of Φ 120mm (Fig.1b). Small addition of B₄C to matrix alloy (Ti-6Al-4V) produce the intermetallic TiB whisker and TiC particle during solidification by the chemical reactions:

The ingot was hot forged into a billet 25 mm in diameter and 1000mm in length, followed by annealing treatment at 600 °C for 30 minutes and air cooling, respectively. Finally, the (TiB+TiC)/Ti6Al4V composite was cut into cubic specimens of 10mm \times 10mm \times 140mm for ECAP processing.

Fig.1 Experimental procedure (a) consumable vacuum arc-remelting furnace (b) the ingot

2.2 ECAP processing

Special die-set with enlarged angles of channel intersection equal to 120° was fabricated to process ECAP alloys. The route Bc was applied, a billet was turned clockwise along its longitudinal axis by 90° after each pass. The pressing temperature was 800°C . A schematic illustration of the ECAP process was shown in Fig.2. In order to investigate the effect of the amount of deformation and pass numbers on the microstructure and properties of (TiB+TiC)/Ti6Al4V composite. For each pass, the ECAP die was heated to 550°C , and the cubic specimen was held for 20min to reach the temperature stabilization. Before inserting into the ECAP die channel, the sample was coated with graphite paste to assure lubrication during ECAP process. After that, the sample was pressed at the speed of 8mm/min, and the samples on each processing were extruded for one, two, three and four passes at the same temperature. The lubricant of graphite paste was also applied to reduce the friction between the die and specimen during the ECAP process. After each ECAP process, the sample should be quickly removed and water quenched to keep the microstructure. Longitudinal sections of the samples were prepared for optical microscopy (OM) and scanning electron microscopy (SEM) analyses.

Fig.2 Schematic diagram showing the continuous ECAP process

2.4 Microstructure and property tests

To observe the microstructural evolution, the deformed specimens were sectioned parallel to compression axis from one side of the deformation specimens, and the cut surface of the smaller part was prepared for metallographic examination by means of optical metallographic (OM) and scanning electron microscopy (SEM). The polished samples were etched with a solution of 30% HNO_3 +10% HF in water for 5 seconds. Tensile tests were performed at room temperature using a universal testing machine Zwick Z100/SN3A. Flat samples with a gage length of 18mm and a cross-section of $3\text{mm} \times 1.6\text{mm}$ were wire Electrical Discharge Machining (EDM) cut from the titanium matrix composite billets. A strain rate of 10-3mm/s was used for the all tests. Yield strength and elongation to failure at the necking cross-section were measured.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Microstructure and phase identification

Fig. 3 shows the appearance of the TiB+TiC/Ti6Al4V titanium matrix composite billets after 1 and 4 ECAP passes at the same pressing speed. In Fig. 3a, it is observed that the microstructure of specimen shows equiaxed structure and the volume fraction of the microstructure consisted of approximately 85% equiaxed α phase, 10% long TiB fibers and large TiC particles. The size of the equiaxed α phase is about 8~10 μm in diameter, TiB fibers is about ~15 μm in length and width of ~3 μm , TiC particle is about 15 μm in diameter with an irregular shape. Comparing with the first ECAP pass, the specimen after 4 ECAP passes showed that the surfaces of the samples are smooth and some small metal flash existed. Nevertheless, close inspections revealed that cracks appeared on the sample which was processed by 4 ECAP passes, and the microstructure showed the TiB and TiC reinforcements dispersed homogeneous in the composite. Fig.4 shows the X-ray diffraction patterns for initial and ECAP-processed samples. It indicates that there are four kinds of phases in the composites, α -Ti, β -Ti, TiB and TiC. The results of X-ray diffraction analysis confirms that the (TiB+TiC)/Ti6Al4V titanium matrix composite could be fabricated by common casting technique using chemical reaction between titanium matrix metal and B4C powder. Comparing with different ECAP passes, there is no significant difference in the X-ray diffraction patterns.

Fig.3 Appearance of the titanium matrix composite billets after 1 and 4 ECAP passes

Fig.4 X-ray diffraction patterns (a) Initial material, (b) 1 pass (c) 2 passes (d) 3 passes (e) 4 passes

3.1 Microstructure of first ECAP pass

Fig.5 illustrates SEM photomicrograph of the first ECAP pass TiB+TiC/Ti6Al4V composite. After the first ECAP pass, partial reinforcements were subjected to breakage. Primary equiaxed α phases were elongated in an angle, lamellar secondary α phase generated a twisting phenomenon due to the bear the shear deformation of die angle of 120°. Meanwhile, lots of nearly acicular α phases with thickness of about 0.6 μm were observed in the transformed β phase, which could be fractured easily in the following high strains, resulting much more ultrafine grains in nanoscale. The breakage of reinforcements can be explained as a result of the following reasons: first, the shearing action which is

generated in the matrix by ECAP can directly break the reinforcements. Second, the compressive stresses generated during ECAP could cause the crushing of the reinforcements. It is noted that this broken reinforcement mainly existed in the rear part of the specimen.

Fig.6 shows the microstructure of the second ECAP pressed sample. In Fig. 6a, it shows the distribution of TiB fiber and TiC particles in the 2 passes ECAP pressed composite. The distribution is fairly uniform but there are much more segregation of reinforcement (Fig. 6b and 6c). From Fig. 6b and 6c, obvious orientation in the matrix structure can be observed and that is about 45° angle between deformation structure orientation and horizontally flowing direction. Although a majority of reinforcements was distributed along the above described orientation, there are also few zones distributed in other direction far from the main direction. The TiC particles were refined to nearly ~6µm in width, and a large number of defects were observed in the TiC particles, which could be the generation of the crack initiation, resulting in failure in further ECAP pass. Fig. 6d and Fig. 6e shows the fractured TiB fibers and broken TiC particles. It indicated that TiB fibers and TiC particles have experienced a severe breakage after 2 ECAP passes, which was responsible for the decrease of the reinforcements by the intensive plastic straining during ECAP.

Fig.5 SEM image of the first ECAP pressed sample

Fig.6 Microstructure of the second ECAP pressed sample

- (a) Macrostructure of reinforcements (b) Fractured reinforcements (c) Defects in TiC particles (d) Fractured TiB fiber (e) Broken TiC particles

3.2 Microstructure of four ECAP passes

After four ECAP passes, a considerable refined TiB and TiC was observed (Fig. 7). Fig. 7a illustrates a large decrease in reinforcement size is obtained. The reinforcement size decreased from

~15 μm to ~5 μm . The effect of further passes on reinforcement breakage decreases gradually and is more pronounced. The corresponding EDX taken on the particle confirms the nearly equiaxed particles to be TiC. There is no evident particle orientation observed after four ECAP passes. However, as can be seen from Fig.7b and Fig.7c, it clearly shown that broken TiC particles and fractured TiB fibers existed in the matrix alloy, a reinforcement debonding has taken place in the reinforcement-matrix interface. In a composite the load is transferred from the matrix to the stronger reinforcement via the reinforcement-matrix interface. The high shear strains generated in the ECAP process might have led to the separation at the interface.

Fig.7 Microstructure of the four ECAP pressed sample (a) Refined reinforcements (b) Broken TiC particles (c) Fractured TiB fiber

3.3 Tensile property

Tensile test curves for the number of ECAP processed billets were plotted in Fig. 8. The mechanical properties were obtained by the methods mentioned in section 2.4. It could be seen clearly that the influence of the number of passes on mechanical property is obvious. After the first pass, the tensile strength of the ECAP processed billets increases significantly to 1150MPa, while the elongation is only 2.7%. Then the plasticity is improved as the number of pass increasing, the tensile ductility increases up to the biggest value (4.5%) in the four ECAP passes. Comparing with other materials which are subjected to rolling deformation, the strength should increase while the plasticity decreases in a certain amount. But for the ECAP processed titanium matrix composite, the plasticity is improved with the increase of pass number. The reason of the improvement is attributing to the phase boundaries increasing resulted from the refinement of reinforcement and the grain size after one ECAP pass number. The effect of work hardening behavior becomes obvious gradually after three passes, while the tensile strength decreases slightly after four passes. The decrease of strength and the increase of ductility could be the interaction of refinement and working hardening. During the first ECAP pass, the refinement of TiB fibers and TiC particles would enhance the dislocations, which results in dislocation density increasing quickly in the boundary of the refinements, and the work hardening phenomenon is serious. After the four passes, the ductility increases to 4.5%, it is attributed to the annihilation of the dislocations. As a result, (TiB+TiC)/Ti6Al4V composite processed exhibits higher elongation but similar strength compared with the sample ECAP processed after the first pass.

Fig.8 Tensile test curves for the ECAP processed billets for different passes

Fig.9 SEM micrographs of longitudinal sections of different deformed areas in the fractured sample of in situ (TiB+TiC)/Ti6Al4V

From above results, it is clear that the mechanical behavior of different ECAP passes differs from each other. The difference in the ductility levels can be attributed to their reinforcements' difference and also slight variations in the strength. Although their ECAP procedure is quite similar, resulting in the microstructure of matrix metal is similar for each pass, this shows the effectiveness of reinforcements in achieving smaller grain sizes in titanium matrix composite. Fig.9 shows the SEM images of titanium matrix composite near fracture surfaces after room temperature tensile test. It can be seen that the reinforcements play an important role on the tensile properties of the composite. In the ECAP process, some long TiB fibers (with high aspect ratio) near fracture surface fractured, this indicates that the TiB fibers are bearing the tensile stress in the room tensile tests. The fracture mechanism was quite typical for titanium composite at room tensile test. Meanwhile, some large TiC particles severely break with an angle of about 60° along the tensile direction. There is an interfacial debonding behavior happened between the TiB short fibers and the matrix alloy, which resulting in cracking. According to the study by Bowen, et al [21], large shear strain was drawn in the ECAP process. After four ECAP passes, the TiB fibers and TiC particles size are decreasing heavily, interfacial debonding is easy to take place in the two ends of the reinforcement, which is due to a concentration of stress in the end of the reinforcement with the increase of the shear strain. Furthermore, lots of cavities will immediately generate around the TiB fibers and TiC particles. It could be one of the dominant reasons for the failure of the sample extruded in the next ECAP pass. Fig. 9a shows some cracks generated around the TiB short fibers, and a few broken TiC particles are gathering together. It is found that the reinforcements' load-bearing effect would be less dominant than the dislocation density effect for the refinement of the reinforcement dispersion strengthening.

5 CONCLUSIONS

- (1). Equal channel angular pressing of a titanium matrix composite reinforced with TiB fibers and TiC particles was successfully carried out up to 4 ECAP passes.
- (2). Significant breaking of reinforcements was a result of ECAP procedures. After 4 ECAP passes, the TiC particle size decreased from ~15 μm to ~5 μm , the average length of TiB fibers decreased from ~15 μm to 5 μm .
- (3). Breaking of the reinforcements was observed to be a result of brittle fracture in the reinforcements by the severe plastic deformation during ECAP.
- (4). (TiB+TiC)/Ti6Al4V composite processed exhibits higher elongation but similar strength compared with the sample ECAP processed after the first pass.
- (5). The enhancement of ductility is dominated by the decreasing of reinforcements' size, and the homogeneity of the reinforcements' distribution through four passes is better than that through one pass.

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